

Similarly, other 2-azetidiones were prepared (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 6*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	Phenyl	210	68
2.	4-Tolyl	192	52
3.	2-Chlorophenyl	259	70
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	248	72
5.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	271	60
6.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	238	68
7.	2-Methoxyphenyl	278	71
8.	4-Methoxyphenyl	213	61
9.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	251	58
10.	3-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl	178	60
11.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	185	52
12.	2-Nitrophenyl	217	67
13.	3-Nitrophenyl	243	60
14.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	256	62
15.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	158	78

*All the compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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Synthesis of 3-(p diazobenzoyl Nβ-arylidinohydrazone)indoles

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3-SUBSTITUTED-indoles are well-known for their pharmacological and biochemical activities¹. Hydrazone derivatives find considerable use in chemotherapy, mostly as antitubercular agents². Since the use of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH)

as a clinically effective antitubercular drug, a large number of acid hydrazides and their condensation derivatives have been prepared and tested for antitubercular properties. They have also been found to possess various biological activities³.

Keeping this in view, we have studied the synthesis (Scheme 1) and antimicrobial activities of some 3-(p-diazobenzoyl-Nβ-arylidinohydrazone)-indoles. The structure of the compounds have

been established on the basis of their elemental analyses, m.m.p. and ir spectral data. The ir spectra of the compounds show characteristic bands at 3 420 (NH), 1 500 and 1 530 (C-H and C-C stretching and deformation vibration of indole heterocycle), 1 665 (C=N), 1 575 (N=N), 1 620 (NHCO) and 840 cm^{-1} (1,4-disubstituted benzene).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

p-Aminobenzoyl-Nβ-arylidinohydrazines (2)⁴: A mixture of *p*-aminobenzoylhydrazide (1) and appropriate aldehyde in ethanol was kept at room

temperature for 24 h, and then filtered and recrystallised from alcohol.

3-(p-Diazobenzoyl-Nβ-arylidinohydrazono)indoles (4): Compound 2 (0.01 mol) in dilute HCl was diazotised at 0° with NaNO₂ and then added slowly to a solution of indole (0.01 mol) in dilute KOH (10%) containing crushed ice. The resulting red solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Sl. no.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	146	65
2.	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	144	64
3.	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	124	69
4.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₃	142	71
5.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃	158	68
6.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	103	64
7.	3,4(O-CH ₃ O)-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	167	66
8.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃	97	65
9.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₃	154	67
10.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₃	151	69
11.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O	147	64
12.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O	158	68
13.	5-Br-2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ BrN ₅ O ₃	150	70
14.	5-Br-4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ BrN ₅ O ₃	126	65
15.	5-I-4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ IN ₅ O ₃	144	67

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Pharmacological screening: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Representative compounds were screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v).

Out of 15 compounds, 8 compounds were found to be active against *S. aureus* and 7 compounds active against *E. coli*, and 5 compounds active against both the species. Compounds having 4-methoxyphenyl, 4-methylphenyl, 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl and 4-chlorophenyl substitutions were found active against both the species.

Out of 8 compounds screened, 3 compounds were effective at both the concentrations (35 and 100 μg ml⁻¹). Two compounds were found effective only at higher concentration. Compounds having 2-hydroxyphenyl, 2-chlorophenyl and 5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl substitutions were found effective at both the concentrations.

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Synthesis of some Aminoacetamide Derivatives

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IN continuation of our work on acetamide derivatives¹, we have synthesised some 1(H)-4-(N'-arylaminoacetamido)-5-carbethoxy-pyrimidin-2-ones (3) with a view to get better therapeutic agents. 5-Carbethoxycytosine (1) prepared by the reported method², was chloroacetylated with chloroacetylchloride in benzene to get 4-N-chloroacetyl-5-carbethoxycytosine (2), which on condensation with various aromatic amines yielded compound 3 (Scheme 1).

The structures of 1-3 were supported by elemental analysis and ir spectra. The ir spectrum of 1 showed characteristic bands and 3 450 (NH for free NH₂) and 3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH for pyrimidine ring). The peak at 3 450 cm⁻¹ disappeared and a new peak appeared at 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=O for CONH) in the ir spectra of compound 2. Moreover, compounds 1-3 gave characteristic bands at 1 560 (C=C), 1 630 (C=N), 3 300 (NH), 1 690 (C=O cyclic), 1 300 (C-N) and 1 730 cm⁻¹ (for ester carbonyl), supporting structures of the compounds.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesised compounds was checked on tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.